
Full Paper

GENETIC NEURO-FUZZY SYSTEM FOR THE IDENTIFICATION OF CITRUS HUANGLONGBING

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ABSTRACT

There is an increasing demand for Citrus; especially for its use in the areas of medicine, juice production, beauty treatment, food spices and other uses. Citrus Huanglongbing (or Greening) are pathogens that affect Citrus production. Infected citrus are not desirable for consumption because of its characteristic bitter taste and increased acidity. Existing manual diagnostic system of Citrus Huanglongbing is prone to errors. This paper applies a soft computing approach that hybridizes Genetic Algorithm, Fuzzy Logic and Neural Network for identifying the presence of pathogens such as Huanglongbing in Citrus plants. The proposed system, which is self-learning, is able to handle uncertainty in the identification process while ensuring optimal result.

Keywords:

Citrus Greening, Citrus Huanglongbing, Genetic Algorithm, Neural Network, Fuzzy Logic

1. INTRODUCTION

The genus Citrus, is a flowering plant of the *Citreae* tribe. It hails from the *Aurantioideae* subfamily of the Rue family – *Rutaceae* of the *Plantae* Kingdom. Citrus is a flowering plant that grows best in a freely draining soil. Citrus can be found in most part of the world especially in tropical and subtropical regions. Common citrus species found in most parts of Africa include Lime (*Citrus aurantifolia*), Lemon (*Citrus Limon*), Grapefruit (*Citrus paradisi*), Sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*), and so on (Krezdorn, 2016; Johnson, 2002).

In most parts of the planet, especially in Nigeria, Citrus fruits can be eaten as fresh fruits or processed into fruit juice as in the case of Sweet Orange, Tangerine, and so on. It can also be added to food or used as medicine or cosmetics as in the case of Lime and Lemon. Citrus fruits are believed to contain a high level of Vitamin C and other essential vitamins. Some citrus species such as Lime can be used as spices in cooked food; while some others such as Sweet Orange and Lemon can have their leaves boiled and served as tea (Manner et al, 2006). Citrus fruits can also be used for beauty therapy. The use of citrus is far-reaching and its use limited to the consumer's knowledge.

Pathogen can be considered the most critical threat to citrus trees. Pathogens are microorganisms that cause diseases in their host. They include bacteria, fungi, viruses and protozoa. It is worthy of note that certain infections such as Huanglongbing has no known cure. Nonetheless, other infections have varying severity levels.

Identifying a particular pathogen could be herculean. It may take a long time for some plant pathogenic organisms to develop disease symptoms after initial infection. Marylou et al (2007) opines that this long latent period results in significantly delayed disease diagnosis and pathogen detection because some of the initial symptoms mimic other infections, mineral deficiencies, or toxicities. For instance, both a nutritional deficiency of citrus plants and Huanglongbing disease could result in yellowing of the leaves. To ensure an accurate diagnosis of the ailment, there has to be a way of properly classifying the infections. This paper proposes a soft computing model that employs Fuzzy Logic, Neural Network and Genetic Algorithm to aid accurate diagnosis of Citrus Huanglongbing.

Soft Computing technique has been successfully applied to solve other kinds of problems. Imianvan and Obi (2011) proposed an expert system that efficiently eliminated the uncertainties in

diagonising Tuberculosis. They noted that Tuberculosis has varying symptoms that could be confused for other ailments, creating an uncertainty that manual method could not sufficiently resolve.

Ekong et al (2011) applied the methodology known as Fuzzy Cluster Means Algorithm for the evaluation, classification and matching of patterns to more than one class of Liver Condition. The work was effectively developed to support the diagnosis of liver condition using a set of clinical sign and symptoms. The system results proved to be an efficient and intelligent way of classifying and matching symptoms of such illnesses.

Soft computing are adaptive, intelligent systems that attempt to mimic human reasoning in dealing with problems of learning, uncertainty and imprecision (Chakraborty, 2010). It mainly comprises a hybrid of fuzzy logic, genetic algorithm, neural networks and probabilistic reasoning. While Neural Network mimics our ability to adapt to circumstances and learn from past experiences, Fuzzy logic tackles imprecision and vagueness in input and output description of the system. Genetic Algorithm mimics biological evolution with its optimised random search characteristics. Genetic algorithms are adaptive heuristic search algorithm. It has its base on the natural selection and genetics in an evolutionary process. Although randomized, they make use of historical information to direct the search into a region of better performance within the search space. The evolution always starts from a population of randomly generated individuals and is an iterative process with the population from such iteration called a generation. Genetic algorithm terminates when either a maximum number of generations has been produced or a satisfactory fitness level has been reached for the population.

This paper applies a hybrid of Genetic algorithm, Fuzzy logic and Neural Network for identifying the presence of pathogens in citrus. The hybridization of these various techniques, harnesses their individual advantages to achieve the best possible solution to a problem.

2. CITRUS PATHOGENS

A pathogen is a microorganism that causes diseases in its host. Pathogens include bacteria, fungi, viruses and protozoa. Unlike physiological disorders and pest effect on citrus plants, pathogen poses a

very critical negative effect. Pathogens are capable of causing diseases that could make a whole orchard unprofitable.

Pathogens can cause the following infections:

- i. Citrus Huanglongbing (or Greening)
- ii. Greasy spot
- iii. Melanose
- iv. Tristeza
- v. Citrus Black Spot
- vi. Citrus Canker
- vii. Phytophthora (root rot, gummosis e.t.c)
- viii. Citrus Scab
- ix. Psorosis-ringspot
- x. Nematodes and so on.

2.1 Citrus Huanglongbing

Citrus Huanglongbing, also known as Citrus Greening, is a bacterial disease that can greatly reduce fruit production and kill trees (McBride et al, 2013). Huanglongbing (HLB) is a Chinese word for “yellow shoot disease” (Marylou et al, 2007). Greening is spread by grafting, by infected citrus seed, and/or flight or wind dispersal of Asian Citrus Psyllid (Grafton-Cardwell et al., 2006). Asian Citrus Psyllid is an aphid-like pest that is believed to be the vector of *Candidatus Liberabacter asiaticus* which causes Huanglongbing disease (Grafton-Cardwell et al., 2006). The Asian Citrus Psyllid is believed to damage plants directly through its feeding activities. It causes the leaf blade attached to the shoots to have blotchy mottling – i.e. marks with spots of different shades/colours (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Citrus greening. (McBride et al, 2013)

HLB is considered the most critical of all infections that affect Citrus (Roistacher, 2006; Marylou et al, 2007; McBride et al, 2013). An infected tree would eventually become unprofitable and unproductive after five (5) to eight (8) years (Roistacher, 2006). Citrus fruits from infected tree are not desirable for consumption due to its bitter taste and increased acidity. It is a globally dreaded bacteria as the infection cannot be pruned away; the infected tree may have to be removed and the stump killed with herbicide to prevent sprouting.

Thus, to ensure disease-free and profitable Citrus plantations, there has to be a consistent monitoring of psyllid vector and timely application of pesticides to prevent spread.

2.2 Symptoms of Citrus Huanglongbing

When a plant is infected with Citrus Huanglongbing, the fruits become smaller and underdeveloped. There may be an orange-brown discoloration on the tissue where the fruit attaches to the tree. The juice from the infected fruit becomes abnormally bitter with high acidity and low in soluble solids. Also, dieback may occur which could result in leafless twigs or branches and fruits may drop prematurely. Notably, the leaves of infected tree are yellowing and appear to have blotchy mottling.

McBride et al (2013) and Marylou et al (2007) agree that Citrus Huanglongbing can be identified by the following symptoms:

- i) Blotchy mottling on leaves
- ii) Dieback on leaves or branches
- iii) Tree is stunted and sparsely foliated
- iv) Asymmetric yellowing of leaves
- v) Fruit is abnormally bitter
- vi) Fruit drops prematurely
- vii) Malformation or crack on fruit

3. METHODOLOGY

Figure 2: Model of the Expert System for Identification of Citrus Huanglongbing

As shown in Figure 2, the Knowledgebase consist of the linguistic variable (fuzzy set or symptoms) for identifying the presence of Citrus Huanglongbing, the Fuzzy-If-Then rules and the generated and optimized universe of discourse values. The Data Mining Engine is where the input data are processed to give a desired output. The model accepts both structured and unstructured data which is duly processed.

There exist several symptoms that show that a Citrus plant could be infected with a disease. To correctly identify the presence of Citrus Huanglongbing, the following symptoms were selected as shown in Table 1. The table also shows the degree to which a particular symptom can be

said to represent the existence of Citrus Huanglongbing on a plant.

As seen in Figure 3, when a Citrus plant indicates blotchy mottling of leaves (D01) it is not infected but requires further investigation. Similarly, if tree is stunted (D03), fruits dropping prematurely (D06) and deformity is noticed on the fruits (D07), this could be a pointer that the plant may be infected with Citrus Huanglongbing. However, the presence of the following – dieback on leaves or branches (D02), asymmetric yellowing of leaves (D04), fruit taste abnormally bitter (D05) – when noticed alongside any previously listed symptoms, confirms the plant is infected with Citrus Huanglongbing.

Table 1: Various forms of Citrus Infections showing their degree of membership function

Symptom Codes	Symptoms/Fuzzy Set (Parameters) For Identification of Citrus Huanglongbing	Degree of Membership Function for Citrus Huanglongbing (Scale ranges from 0.00 – 1.00)		
		Cluster 1 (Not Infected with Huanglongbing)	Cluster 2 (Maybe Infected with Huanglongbing)	Cluster 3 (Infected with Huanglongbing)
D01	Blotchy mottling on leaves	0.30	0.30	0.40
D02	Dieback on leaves or branches	0.15	0.15	0.70
D03	Tree is stunted and sparsely foliated	0.02	0.48	0.50
D04	Asymmetric yellowing of leaves	0.05	0.05	0.90
D05	Fruit is abnormally bitter	0.02	0.06	0.92
D06	Fruit drops prematurely	0.25	0.50	0.25
D07	Malformation or crack on fruit	0.30	0.50	0.20

3.1 Graphical Analysis of Disease Symptoms

Figure 3: A graph showing symptoms of Citrus Huanglongbing Disease

3.2 Genetic and Neuro-Fuzzy Analysis of the system

Convert the values to whole numbers and make them the fitness function (f) of the initial generation parents. The derived values are:

R1: 30; **R2:** 45; **R3:** 40; **R4:** 52;

R5: 54; **R6:** 25; **R7:** 30

In Tables 2, 3, and 4, the genetic selections R_i (where $i = 1$ to 7) are encoded using Binary encoding. Binary encoding is considered the most common encoding method for representing information as chromosomes in bits 0s and 1s. Binary Encoding was used for this study due to its efficient use of genetic operators on it.

Genetic operators are imperative in ensuring genetic diversity or variation from generation to generation. After using the selection method as shown, other genetic operators such as Crossover and Mutation were applied. Crossover basically combines two parent chromosomes to produce a

new offspring chromosome in the next generation. This genetic operator aims to achieve a better offspring generation by taking the best characteristics of both parents. There are several crossover methods which include One-Point Crossover, Two-Point Crossover, Uniform, Arithmetic, and Heuristic Crossovers. The One-Point Crossover method was used for this study; taking the third (3rd) bit as the crossover point.

Furthermore, mutation was performed on some of the genes while applying the Crossover operator (the fifth bit in this case). The mutation operators ensure that a generation of chromosomes do not wholly repeat themselves. A limited number of gene values of a chromosome are altered to maintain genetic diversity and prevent a population from stagnating at any local optima of the search space. This way the search is optimised and a better solution is achieved.

Table 2: Genetic operators used for the selected 1st generation parents

	Selection	Chromosomes			Fitness Function
		Parent (1 st generation)	Crossover/ Mutation	Offspring (2 nd generation)	
1	35	100011	1 & 7	100110	38
2	45	101101	2 & 3	101000	40
3	40	101000	2 & 3	101101	45
4	52	110100	4 & 6	110001	49
5	54	110110	Mutation	100110	38
6	25	011001	4 & 6	011100	28
7	30	011110	1 & 7	011011	27

Table 3: 2nd and 3rd generations of chromosomes evolving

S/N	Selection	Chromosomes			Fitness Function
		Parent (2 nd generation)	Crossover/ Mutation	Offspring (3 rd generation)	
1	38	100110	1 & 6	100100	36
2	40	101000	2 & 5	101110	46
3	45	101101	3 & 7	101011	43
4	49	110001	Mutation	100001	33
5	38	100110	2 & 5	100000	32
6	28	011100	1 & 6	011110	30
7	27	011011	3 & 7	011101	29

From Table 3, the best fitness function is 46 which is at serial number 2. This means that the genetic operation on the state space of the various clusters has searched and produced an optimised value of 0.46. The resultant optimised value is considered closest to the best solution.

Let the presence of citrus infections be classified as follows:

- i. C1: Not Infected with Citrus Huanglongbing Disease
- ii. C2: Maybe Infected with Citrus Huanglongbing Disease
- iii. C3: Infected with Citrus Huanglongbing Disease

If the Citrus under examination is found to possess at least two (2) of the parameters/symptoms then it is not infected with Citrus Disease; hence it is in Class C1. If it exhibits exactly three (3) symptoms then it may be infected with Citrus Disease; hence classify as C2. Otherwise, if symptoms exhibited is four (4) and above then the Citrus is infected with a disease.

Table 4: Membership function and probability of Infection

Membership Function	Infection Probability
< 0.46	Low
≥ 0.46	High

3.3 Fuzzy IF-THEN Rules

The presence of Citrus Huanglongbing can be correctly diagnosed using the Fuzzy IF-THEN rules as shown hereunder; considering Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4.

R1: IF Citrus exhibits blotchy mottling on leaves and infection probability is low THEN it is in Class C1

R2: IF Citrus exhibits blotchy mottling on leaves, malformation or crack on fruit and infection probability is low THEN it is in Class C1

R3: IF Citrus exhibits blotchy mottling on leaves, malformation or crack on fruit, Tree is stunted and sparsely foliated and infection probability is high THEN it is in Class C2

R4: IF Citrus exhibits blotchy mottling on leaves, malformation or crack on fruit, Tree is stunted and sparsely foliated, fruit drops prematurely and infection probability is high THEN it is in Class C3

R5: IF Citrus exhibits blotchy mottling on leaves, malformation or crack on fruit, Tree is stunted and sparsely foliated, fruit drops prematurely, asymmetric yellowing of leaves and infection probability is high THEN it is in Class C3

R6: IF Citrus exhibits blotchy mottling on leaves, malformation or crack on fruit, Tree is stunted and sparsely foliated, fruit drops prematurely, asymmetric yellowing of leaves, dieback on leaves/branches and infection probability is high THEN it is in Class C3

R7: IF Citrus exhibits blotchy mottling on leaves, malformation or crack on fruit, Tree is stunted and sparsely foliated, fruit drops prematurely, asymmetric yellowing of leaves, dieback on leaves/branches, fruit is abnormally bitter and infection probability is high THEN it is in Class C3.

4. CONCLUSION

Citrus are plants with large shrubs or small trees cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions. Some Citrus species include Lime, Sweet Orange, Tangerine, and Grapefruit among others. The quality of fruits produced by Citrus plants can be hampered by disorders or the effects of pathogens. Infected fruits can grossly affect the economic benefit to the farmer, hence an early detection and correct identification of Citrus infections is imperative.

Citrus Huanglongbing, also known as Citrus Greening, is a pathogenic disease that poses a devastating effect on citrus plants that could cause low productivity of infected plants or death in cases of severe infection.

This paper uses Genetic Neuro-Fuzzy system for the identification of Citrus Infection which is a soft

computing approach aimed at precise identification of Citrus infection. It integrates the advantages and capabilities of Genetic Algorithm, Neural Networks, and Fuzzy Logic. It produces reliable solution to incomplete and imprecise information.

Existing manual diagnostic system of Citrus Huanglongbing is prone to errors. This paper has shown that the proposed Genetic Neuro-Fuzzy System is preferable for the identification of Citrus Infections such as Huanglongbing. The proposed system which is self-learning is able to handle uncertainty in the identification process while ensuring optimal result. The system was simulated and found to be effective in determining the presence of an infection in Citrus.

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